

Studies in Organo-arsenic Compounds. Part II.

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No attempt appears hitherto have been made to introduce arsenic into xanthone nucleus. The only compound that is known to contain arsenic is xanthoarsenite, a naturally occurring mineral, discovered by Igelström (*Z. Kryst. Min.*, 1886, 10, 518).

Xanthone itself possesses antiseptic action and the assumption that by introducing arsenic into the nucleus, the resulting compounds might prove to have greater potentialities as drugs, led to the present attempts. The different compounds that have been prepared are the following: Xanthone-3-arsinic acid, α -nitroxantharsinic acid, β -nitroxantharsinic acid, β -aminoxantharsinic acid, β -acetylaminoxantharsinic acid, and bromonitroxantharsinic acid.

The next series of compounds that have been described are the quinoline derivatives of coumarin and xanthone containing arsenic in the nucleus. Of these the first compound is a pseudo oxazone and contains, in addition to the pyridine ring, groups like $\text{CH}:\text{CH}$ - and $\text{-O}\cdot\text{CO}$ in the ring. The existence of the above mentioned groupings in a compound causes the augmentation of the number of polymorphonuclear white blood corpuscles, helping there by in an indirect way, in checking an attack due to parasites, and increased internal secretions. It has also been definitely established that quinoline compounds have decided antipyretic action, specially if the position-6 is fixed and an enhanced action is observed if both 4- and 6-positions are simultaneously occupied. The compound ψ -1:8-isonaphthoxazone-3-arsinic acid, described in this paper, in which the positions 4 and 6 are occupied, satisfy all the above mentioned conditions in addition to the pentavalent arsenic in the nucleus and was, therefore, supposed to have an enhanced antipyretic and bactericidal action in the treatment of diseases due to parasitic organism.

The nitro- ψ -1:8-isonaphthoxazone was prepared according to the method of Dey and Goswami (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 115, 531) for the preparations of coumaroquinoline from nitrocoumarins. The provisional formula as advanced by the authors (*loc. cit.*) has been adopted.

The reduction of the nitro- ψ -oxazone was effected by sulphuretted hydrogen and ammonia in alcoholic solution. It is probable that upto the formation of the arsenic acid derivative the following has been the main course.

The application of the Skraup reaction was extended to the other dinitro derivatives of coumarin, *e.g.*, 7-methyl- and 4:7-dimethyl-3:6-dinitrocoumarins and in each case the desired product was obtained but the yield was too low to be used for subsequent treatments.

The second compound xanthoquinoline- β -arsinic acid was prepared from β -aminoxanthoquinoline. The nitro compound was prepared by Dhar (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 117, 1053). Here also it will be found that the position -4 or 6 is occupied and from similar arguments should have antiseptic and bactericidal activity as will be evident from the following constitutional formula.

The arsenic acids, enumerated as above, had all been prepared by the well-known Bart's reaction from their corresponding amino derivatives. The reduction of β -nitroxantharsinic acid was done by the

method of Jacob, Heidelberger and Rolf (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1918, 40, 1580) most easily. The method claimed by Fargher (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 115, 990) to give satisfactory results and which is a modification of that described in D. R. P. 224953, for the method of reduction of nitroarsinic acids failed to do the same in this particular case. Monobromodinitroxanthone and β -nitroxanthoquinoline had been reduced by ammonia and sulphuretted hydrogen in alcoholic solution. The method for the reduction of 3-nitroxanthone, α - and β -dinitroxanthone, as suggested by Dhar (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, 109, 744), gave very low yield of the amino derivatives. The additional disadvantage of the method is that on account of the lower solubility of the nitrocompounds in alcohol, a large quantity of the solvent is required to start with. To obviate this difficulty the nitro derivatives had been reduced by stannous chloride in alcohol and hydrochloric acid solution. In the cases of α - and β -derivatives, contrary to the usual expectation, namely, the simultaneous reduction of both the nitro groupings, in each case a nitroamino compound was obtained. The reduction products were tested both qualitatively and quantitatively to ascertain the similarity of the compounds with those obtained by reducing with sulphuretted hydrogen and ammonia as tried by Dhar (*loc. cit.*) and the identity was observed in each case.

The arsenic acids vary in coloration, from brown to yellow, and most of them are nearly insoluble in commoner organic solvents. They are all microcrystalline solids, readily soluble in caustic alkalis and alkaline carbonates. The alkaline solutions are deep brown in colour from which hydrochloric acid precipitates the original compounds.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Reduction of Nitroxanthones.

3-Aminoxanthone.—3-Nitroxanthone (7 g.) was gradually added to a mixture, consisting of stannous chloride (21 g.), alcohol (20 c.c.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (18 c.c.), heated in a beaker to a clear solution by direct flame. While the addition of the nitro compound was made the flame was turned low. Within a very short time a slow reaction began and this was over when every thing went into solution. To the reaction mixture concentrated hydrochloric acid (36 c.c.) was added whereby light yellowish white feathery mass immediately separated out. This was allowed to cool and then

filtered. The residue was washed repeatedly with concentrated hydrochloric acid and was then dissolved by boiling in excess of water and filtered. The filtrate was cooled somewhat and sulphuretted hydrogen was passed to precipitate the tin. The resulting mixture was filtered and treated with ammonia when a yellow precipitate of 3-aminoxanthone was obtained. The amino compound was separated, dried, and crystallised from alcohol, m. p. 232°. The other properties of the compound were found to tally with that prepared by Dhar (*loc. cit.*).

α-Nitroaminoxanthone was prepared in a similar manner as above, with the following reaction mixture: *α*-dinitroxanthone (7.5 g.), stannous chloride (22 g.), hydrochloric acid (20 c.c.) and alcohol (30 c.c.). Towards the end of the reaction 35 c.c. more of the concentrated hydrochloric acid were added. The reaction was a rapid one and only one of the nitro groups underwent reduction to amino compound. The substance was crystallised from alcohol, m. p. 205°-07°. (Found: N, 10.78. $C_{13}H_8O_4N_2$ requires N, 10.9 per cent.).

β-Nitroaminoxanthone was prepared in a similar manner and with the same proportions as the *α*-derivative, m. p. 264-65°.

Monobromonitroaminoxanthone.—The reduction of the monobromodinitroxanthone was effected by sulphuretted hydrogen and ammonia in alcoholic solution. The substance was sparingly soluble in alcohol and hence a large excess of the solvent was required. The addition of ammonia was made in two or three portions and sulphuretted hydrogen was passed after each addition. When the reduction was over, the excess of alcohol was evaporated off on a water-bath and the solid mass was treated with a few c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid so as to form a paste. The paste was boiled with excess of water and then filtered from insoluble unchanged nitro compound. The filtrate on being rendered alkaline with ammonia gave yellow crystals of the amino compound. This was recrystallised from alcohol in fine needles, m. p. 143-45°. (Found: N, 8.4. $C_{13}H_7O_4N_2Br$ requires N, 8.3 per cent.).

Introduction of Arsenic in Xanthenes.

3-Xantharsinic Acid.

3-Aminoxanthone (2.2 g.) was suspended in 20 c.c. of water and was dissolved by stirring in hydrochloric acid (2 c.c.). The solution was diazotised at 0° with a solution of sodium nitrite (0.8 g.) in water (5 c.c.) and was then introduced gradually in cooled mixture containing sodium carbonate (10 g.), arsenious oxide (4.5 g.), copper sulphate (0.3 g.) and water (25 c.c.), the whole being well stirred during the operation. The mass became reddish brown and nitrogen evolved and stirring was continued for 1 hour more. The reddish brown solution was concentrated and filtered. The filtrate was gradually acidified with hydrochloric acid till a small quantity of brown precipitate was produced. At this stage the mixture was filtered and the filtrate on further acidification gave a dull yellow precipitate. This was collected, redissolved in sodium bicarbonate, boiled with animal charcoal and filtered. The filtrate was then acidified when whitish yellow microcrystalline powder was obtained. The substance was found to be insoluble in most of the commoner organic solvents and hence the final purification was made by redissolving in sodium bicarbonate and reprecipitating it. It does neither melt nor shrink even upto 335°. (Found: As, 22.9. $C_{13}H_9O_5As$ requires As, 23.4 per cent.).

α-Nitroxantharsinic Acid.

This was prepared in a similar way as the previous compound by diazotising α -nitroaminoxanthone and adding the diazo solution to the arsenite solution. The resulting solution was of deep red colour and this on acidification gave at first a small quantity of scaly precipitate. At this stage the solution was again filtered and the filtrate on further acidification produced a brownish red product. The substance was observed to be readily soluble in alkalis and alkali carbonates and insoluble in most of the commoner organic solvents. Hence it was purified by dissolving in sodium carbonate, boiling the solution with animal charcoal, filtering and then reprecipitating with acid, when dull red microcrystalline product was obtained. It does

not melt even upto 330° , yield 60 p. c. (Found: As, 20.1. $C_{13}H_8O_7NA_s$ requires As, 20.5 per cent.).

β -Nitroxantharsinic Acid.

The acid was prepared and purified in a similar way as the compound from β -nitroaminoxanthone. The substance dissolves readily in alkalis and alkali carbonates but is insoluble in most of the organic solvents. It does not melt even upto 340° , yield 65 p. c. (Found: As, 20.28. $C_{13}H_8O_7NA_s$ requires As, 20.5 per cent.).

β -Aminoxantharsinic acid.—Ordinary ferrous sulphate (10.6 g.) was dissolved in warm water (35 c. c.) The solution was cooled well and was transferred to a wide-mouthed bottle fitted with a rubber stopper. This was treated with 25 p. c. solution of sodium hydroxide till the ferrous hydroxide mud reacted strongly alkaline to litmus paper on vigorous shaking. β -Nitroxantharsinic acid (3.5 g.) was dissolved in sodium hydroxide and this solution was poured at once into the hydroxide mixture, the whole being vigorously shaken for 5 minutes. The alkaline solution was allowed to stand for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour more and during this time the pale blue hydroxide gradually changed in colour to dark brown ferric hydroxide. The mud was separated by filtration through a large buckner funnel, the residue being finally washed with water. The filtrate was next acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid whereby yellow amino compound was precipitated. This was crystallised from acetic acid. Does not melt even upto 347° . (Found: As, 22.1. $C_{13}H_{10}O_5NA_s$ requires As, 22.3 per cent.).

β -Acetylaminoxantharsinic acid.—The sparingly soluble β -aminoxantharsinic acid was finely powdered and suspended in glacial acetic acid. To this excess of acetyl chloride was added and the mixture was heated under reflux for 2 hours. The hot reaction mixture was rapidly filtered and the filtrate was heated on a water-bath to expel the excess of acetyl chloride. The concentrated solution was then treated with cold water when the β -acetyl derivative separated out. The compound was filtered and then dried in a vacuum desiccator and it was finally crystallised as a yellow powder from acetic acid. The compound does neither melt nor shrink even up to 340° ,

yield 85 p. c. (Found: As, 19.5. $C_{15}H_{12}O_6NAs$ requires As, 19.8 per cent.).

Bromonitroantharsinic acid was prepared from monobromonitroaminooxanthone as before by the usual Bart reaction. The substance was purified by alternately dissolving in alkali and reprecipitating with dilute hydrochloric acid. The purified product is of cream coloured microcrystalline powder, m. p. 258-60° (decomp.). (Found: As, 16.57. $C_{13}H_7O_7NBrAs$ requires As, 16.8 per cent.).

Quinoline Derivatives.

3-Nitro-ψ-1:8-isonaphthoxazone.—3:6-Dinitrocoumarin (4 g.) was dissolved to a clear solution in concentrated sulphuric acid (7c. c.). To this solution glycerol (10 c. c.) was added, the addition of which caused the precipitation of the nitro compound with rise in temperature. This was stirred well and was allowed to cool to the room temperature. The cooled mixture was gradually heated in an oil-bath with constant stirring. The mass began to darken at 115° and a vigorous reaction took place between 138-40°. The vessel containing the reaction mixture was removed and allowed to cool with stirring. This was again heated on the bath to 120° and was kept at 135-40° for 1 hour. The temperature was next raised to 150.60° and allowed to remain at this for 5 hours. Finally the temperature was raised to 170° for ½ hour. The black residue was finally powdered, repeatedly boiled with water and filtered after each time. The yellow filtrate was at first treated with concentrated ammonia and then with dilute ammonia whereby voluminous yellowish white precipitate was obtained. The addition of ammonia should be a gradual one as the substance is soluble in excess of the same. The precipitate was separated and then dried in a vacuum desiccator. It was crystallised from alcohol in colourless needles, m. p. 228-30°, yield 2.1 g. (Found: N, 11.48. $C_{12}H_6O_4N_2$ requires N, 11.57 per cent.).

3-Amino-ψ-1:8-isonaphthoxazone.—The nitro compound (5 g.) was dissolved by heating on a water-bath in alcohol. To the clear solution concentrated ammonia (20 c.c.) was added and sulphuretted hydrogen was passed in for 15 minutes. The addition of the latter substance at first gave a precipitate which dissolved to a yellow solution afterwards. The yellow solution was again heated and sulphu-

retted hydrogen passed after adding 20 c.c. more of ammonia. The reduction was complete when the solution assumed a brown coloration. The excess of alcohol was boiled off on a water-bath and concentrated hydrochloric acid was added to the residue so as to get a pasty mass. This was boiled with excess of water and filtered from the insoluble nitro compound. The filtrate was rendered alkaline whereby brownish yellow precipitate was obtained. The amino compound was crystallised from alcohol in light yellow fine needles, m. p. 270°, yield 30 p. c. (Found: N, 13·04. $C_{12}H_8O_2N_2$ requires N, 13·2 per cent.).

ψ-1:8-isonaphthoxazone-3-arsinic acid.—The amino compound described above was dissolved by heating in a solution of hydrochloric acid (1·5 c.c. in 10 c.c. water). The hot solution was rapidly cooled with ice so as to get the hydrochloride in a fine state of subdivision. To the well-cooled solution powdered ice was added and then a solution of sodium nitrite (0·5 g. in 5 c.c. water) was added at one time with stirring. The resulting diazo solution was gradually added with stirring to a well-cooled solution of sodium carbonate (6 g.), arsenious acid (2·5 g.), copper sulphate (0·2 g.) and water (30 c.c.). The addition of the diazo solution caused a slight frothing which subsided with time. The mass was stirred for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour more and was then allowed to stand for 1 hour at the room temperature. The yellowish brown solution was filtered from the suspended and insoluble substances and was next concentrated to a small bulk. Towards the end the whole was boiled for sometime with animal charcoal and filtered. The filtrate on cooling was acidified at first with concentrated and then with dilute hydrochloric acid when a brown precipitate of the arsenic acid derivative was obtained. The precipitate was separated and then dried in a vacuum desiccator. It was crystallised from acetic acid in cream coloured microcrystalline powder, m. p. 225-27° (decomp.). (Found: As, 22·9. $C_{12}H_8O_5N$ As requires As, 23·3 per cent.).

β-Aminoxanthoquinoline was prepared by the reduction of nitroxanthoquinoline by sulphuretted hydrogen and ammonia in alcoholic solution. The substance was crystallised from alcohol in light crystals, m. p. 276-78°. (Found: N, 10·5. $C_{16}H_{10}O_2N_2$ requires N, 10·6 per cent.).

Xanthoquinoline-β-arsinic acid was prepared from *β*-aminoxanthoquinoline by subjecting it to Bart reaction. The acid thus obtained was purified by repeatedly dissolving in alkali and reprecipitating

with acid. This gave the substance as a light brown powder and was found to shrink at 315° but did not melt even up to 345° . (Found: As, 20.08. $C_{16}H_{10}O_3NAs$ requires As, 20.2 per cent.).

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